

THE ROLE OF FAMILY AND NEIGHBORHOOD COMMUNITY ASSOCIATIONS IN EDUCATION OF A PROFESSIONAL GENERATION

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Abstract: In this article, it is stated that the family as the main branch of the state affects the worldview, behavior and taste of children, and that the spiritual unity of family members is one of the first and main factors of all-round development of young people. Information is given that all work in the field of education cannot be successfully carried out without a strong connection between the school and the family, in order to raise children to become well-rounded people.

Key words: family, mature generation, outlook, school, neighborhood.

In our country, taking care of children and mothers is a matter of real national importance. The slogan "All the good things are for children" is sounding even louder. The decisions made on this issue in the following years are proof of our opinion.

It is known that a child is brought up mainly in the family before he comes to school and during his schooling. It is natural that the family, as the main branch of the state, influences the outlook, behavior and taste of children. The spiritual unity of family members is one of the first and main factors for the all-round development of young people.

All work in the field of education cannot be successfully carried out without a strong connection between the school and the family, in order to raise children to become well-rounded people. For this purpose, it is necessary to expand educational campaigns among parents, turning them into active assistants of the school, useful organizers of students in their activities outside the classroom and outside the school.

The rapid development of society, the increasing complexity of activities lead to the increase of invisible effects on the mind of a person. In this situation, a person's current knowledge, skills, and abilities are lacking. First of all, people feel the need for taste, insight, intelligence, manners, and emotional culture, which is formed in the family. Aesthetic, moral and other educational qualities are becoming a necessity of everyday life. Naturally, such qualities are founded and perfected through family upbringing. True, the role of social education in this cannot be denied. From this point of view, if we rely on their unity and mutual cooperation, it is possible to achieve success in education of a well-rounded person. Family education is one of the complex problems in pedagogy. Its complexity lies in the fact that each family is a primitive group of its own, and education is based only on the characteristics of this group.

As we noted, replacing family education with social education has a negative impact on children's development. For example, young children who did not go to kindergartens, but grew up only in the family and reached adulthood, when they go to school, stand out among their peers in many ways. The family's material and spiritual care and upbringing of children cannot be replaced by kindergarten education, and on the contrary, kindergarten education

cannot be replaced by family education. Only mutual cooperation gives a chance to solve the problem positively.

family , with its characteristics and unique influence, remains an important factor in child education. As we have observed in practice, a child's feelings towards his parents and relatives are formed on the basis of his parents' love and caress. A child's respect for his father is the basis for putting his mother's respect in place. Mother's love is ultimately reflected in the relationship with his family, wife, and children.

On the other hand, children also influence their parents. Family relations are the cause of improvement of feelings of family interest, spiritual satisfaction.

Demandingness of parents to themselves and their children, mutual relations between adults and children, friendly environment, trust and mutual understanding are among the important factors of family, school and community in the field of child education. The political awareness of parents plays an important role in the realization of such unity. Because the activity of parents is reflected in family life. In this sense, children regulate their behavior and respect their parents based on their political and civic views.

Family - neighborhood - kindergarten - school - higher and secondary special education - all educational and educational, educational and cultural promotion and campaigning works are systematic, strong cooperation, consistency, unity , the family will be able to fully fulfill its social duties in the development of society only if it is organized on the basis of the principles of succession.

One of the important factors of the economic, socio-political and spiritual growth of our republic is the activity of the family, neighborhood, and school aimed at implementing the educational process. In the "Law on Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention was paid to the role of the family in raising a perfect person who realizes his responsibility to the society and the state. In this regard, the creation of the "Family-neighborhood-school" program is important.

The neighborhood plays a big role in raising children in the family. Since ancient times, the Uzbek people have lived in harmony with the community and shared family customs and traditions with them.

The neighborhood has been fulfilling the task of a community that unites people, has social-political, cultural-educational and educational significance. The school carries out pedagogical education of the population, first of all, parents, supports the creation of an environment of mutual respect, mutual help, human relations in every family, provides financial support to children of large and low-income families. in the way of demonstration, the citizen reveals his educational possibilities in the implementation of the compassion program. The family, on the other hand, closely supports the school in restructuring the educational process and closely supports the school team so that the students acquire all aspects of education.

That is why the issue of family, school and community cooperation is the main requirement of the current era. The school has pedagogically competent, purposeful factors and wide possibilities of educational influence. If the educational activities conducted outside the school do not follow the pedagogical and psychological rules, if the demands of the school, family and society are not the same in the educational process, in some cases children with difficult upbringing appear in the family, and complex problems arise. An important means of

preventing such a situation is to provide educational work on the basis of a family-neighborhood and school cooperation program.

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